

Study of Some Mixed Complexes of Yttrium(III)

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The tendency of 1 : 1 Y(III)-Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and N-Hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) chelates to form mixed ligand, 1 : 1 : 1 chelates with 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid (OSA), 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline 5-sulphonic acid (IOSA). Pyrogallol (PGL), Protocatechuic acid (PCA) and 3,5 dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) has been investigated by potentiometric method at three different temperatures and at fixed ionic strength $\mu = 0.2$.

THE tendency of lanthanides to expand their coordination number, greater than six has been reported by different workers, in the study of the mixed ligand complexes¹⁻⁴.

The present communication describes the results obtained on the study of some mixed ligand complexes of yttrium using ethylenediamine-tetraacetic acid (EDTA) and N-hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) as primary ligands (A) and 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid (OSA), 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline 5-sulphonic acid (IOSA), pyrogallol (PGL), protocatechuic acid (PCA) and 3,5 dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) as secondary ligand (L). All these ternary systems are being reported here, for the first time. The secondary ligands are chosen in such a manner that exchange does not occur between primary and secondary ligand, i.e., the primary complexes are very stable^{5,6} in comparison to the complexes formed between yttrium(III) and secondary ligand. Modified method of Irving and Rossotti technique have been used⁷.

Experimental

Material :

All chemicals employed were of reagent grade purity. The ligand solutions were prepared using disodium salt of EDTA (BDH), HEDTA (Sigma), DNSA (E. Merck), OSA (E. Merck), IOSA (BDH) and protocatechuic acid (BDH). Pyrogallol was purified and its solution was prepared in oxygen free double distilled water to avoid its oxidation. This solution was always freshly prepared. All ligand solutions were standardised potentiometrically. Metal solution was prepared from $Y(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (BDH) in known quantity of nitric acid, to prevent the hydrolysis and was estimated by complexometric titration⁸.

Procedure :

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration against Sodium hydroxide (1.152M) of four mixtures as described in our earlier papers^{8,4}. The ionic strength of solution was adjusted to 0.2M using an appropriate amount of neutral potassium nitrate

Fig. 1. Titration curve for the yttrium-HEDTA-DNSA mixed ligand complex at 25° at $\mu = 0.2M$.

Curve A : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric acid.

Curve B : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ DNSA

Curve C : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ HEDTA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Y(III)

Curve D : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ HEDTA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ DNSA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Y(III).

solution. Final volume of all the systems was adjusted to 100 ml by using double distilled water. Titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at three different temperatures^{3,4}.

The ratio of Y(III) : Primary ligand : Secondary ligand was always kept 1 : 1 : 1 in each system. Typical plots of pH against volume of alkali have been shown in Fig. 1 and 2 for Y(III)-EDTA-DNSA systems and

Fig. 2. Titration curve for the yttrium-EDTA-DNSA mixed ligand complex at 25° at $\mu=0.2M$.

- Curve A : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric Acid.
- Curve B : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric Acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ DNSA.
- Curve C : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric Acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ EDTA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Y(III).
- Curve D : $1.998 \times 10^{-3}M$ Nitric Acid, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ EDTA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ DNSA, $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Y(III).

Y(III)-HEDTA-DNSA. Similar plots were obtained for other systems also. Titration with 1 : 1 : 2 (Y : A : L) have also been performed. It was found in all cases that the nature of curves tally exactly to 1 : 1 : 1 titration, indicating that further expansion of coordination number of Y(III) is not possible.

Results and Discussions

The values of protonation constants as calculated by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_d values are given in Table-1 and have been taken into account for the calculation of the formation constant of ternary systems.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE PROTONATION CONSTANT OF THE SECONDARY LIGAND AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES. ($\mu=0.2M$)

Ligand	Constants	25°	35°	45°
OSA	$\log K_{1H}^H$	8.34	8.20	8.08
	$\log K_{2H}^H$	3.92	3.82	3.73
IOSA	$\log K_{1H}^H$	6.97	6.74	6.66
	$\log K_{2H}^H$	2.46	2.38	2.28
DNSA	$\log K_{1H}^H$	7.52	7.26	7.21
	$\log K_{2H}^H$	10.98	10.82	10.68
PGL	$\log K_{1H}^H$	8.90	8.71	8.57
	$\log K_{2H}^H$	8.97	8.94	8.84
PCA	$\log K_{1H}^H$	4.51	4.49	4.45
	$\log K_{2H}^H$			

From the titration curves, (Fig. 1 and 2) it is observed that primary complex formation (curve C), takes place at very low pH, and the calculations show that it is stable upto $pH \sim 10$ in both the cases (using EDTA and HEDTA as primary ligands). Primary complex curve C and mixed complex curve D overlap each other at lower pH, indicating that in this range, where primary ligand combines with Y(III), attachment of secondary ligands does not take place. The mixed complex curve D, separates from primary complex curve C at $pH 2.0$ due to self dissociation of the secondary ligand (DNSA). After $pH 4$, mixed complex curve shows the indication of attachment of secondary ligand with yttrium. Since, the dissociation of Y-A does not take place in the range of dissociation of secondary ligand, it can be considered that secondary ligand combines the Y(III)-A. In presence of secondary ligand, formation of Y(III)-A(OH)_n is also suppressed.

The \bar{n} values were calculated taking into consideration the difference from curves C and D from which the difference of curve A and B is subtracted at various pH values^{3,4}. A typical plot of \bar{n} against pL for Y(III)-HEDTA-DNSA and Y(III)-EDTA-DNSA systems have been shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Other systems also have similar plots. The value of $\log K_{ML}^M$ have been evaluated using the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values and are summarised in Table-2. The error limits are of ± 0.06 log units.

An observation of the results reported earlier^{3,4} and also in the present paper on the mixed ligand complexes of yttrium, with different primary ligands (keeping secondary bidentate ligand same), shows that the trend in the stability constant is based on the number of vacant coordination position of yttrium,

Fig. 3. Formation curve of [Y(III)(HEDTA)(DNSA)] at different temperatures.

Fig. 4. Formation curve of [Y(III)(EDTA)(DNSA)] at different temperatures.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Y(III) AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES ($\mu=0.2 M$)

System	Constants	t=25°	t=35°	t=45°
Y(III)-HEDTA-OSA	log K ₁	4.90	4.82	4.75
Y(III)-EDTA-OSA	log K ₁	3.95	3.88	3.82
Y(III)-HEDTA-IOSA	log K ₁	4.68	4.57	4.48
Y(III)-EDTA-IOSA	log K ₁	3.80	3.74	3.60
Y(III)-HEDTA-PGL	log K ₁	5.77	5.44	5.27
Y(III)-EDTA-PGL	log K ₁	5.16	5.09	4.81
Y(III)-HEDTA-PCA	log K ₁	3.87	3.80	3.77
Y(III)-EDTA-PCA	log K ₁	3.45	3.38	3.34
Y(III)-HEDTA-DNSA	log K ₁	3.62	3.53	3.47
Y(III)-EDTA-DNSA	log K ₁	3.25	3.20	3.17

capacity of yttrium to expand its coordination number from six to seven or eight and also on the nature of the primary complex species formed.

Thus, depending on the number of vacant coordination positions, it is found that the mixed complexes with NTA (tetradentate) is more stable than HEDTA (pentadentate) which in turn is more stable than EDTA (hexadentate). When NTA is used as primary ligand, the expansion of coordination number is not required. In case of HEDTA, and EDTA, however, coordination number has to be increased to seven or eight respectively

to account for these mixed ligand complex formation. The expansion of coordination number suggests the formation of less stable complexes is evident from the present study.

[Y(NTA)] and [Y(HEDTA)] primary complex species are neutral in nature and thus, do not repel the incoming negatively charged secondary ligand. EDTA, however, forms a [Y(EDTA)] negatively charged species causing an electrostatic force of repulsion for the incoming negatively charged secondary ligands giving lower stability of mixed ligand complexes of yttrium-EDTA.

The mixed ligand complex of OSA is more stable than that of IOSA as it contains an electron withdrawing iodo group. So the basicity of reagent decreases and it forms less stable complex than OSA. Similarly, in case of PGL, PCA and DNSA the order of stability of mixed complexes decrease as $PGL > PCA > DNSA$.

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References

1. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORASS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 89.
2. U. Y. OZER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1279.
3. A. M. PUJARI and K. N. MUNSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 397.
4. A. M. PUJARI and K. N. MUNSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 192.
5. G. SCHWARZENBACH, R. GUT and G. ANDERREGO, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 937.
6. G. SCHWARZENBACH and R. GUT, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1956, 39, 1589.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. J. JENICKOWA, V. SUK and M. MALAT, *Chem. Listy.*, 1956, 50, 760; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 10595.